

Thermodynamic and surface properties of binary liquid alloys

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Abstract : The first order interaction parameters using Maclaurin infinite series have been used to investigate thermodynamic and surface properties of binary liquid alloys. The evaluated excess free energy of mixing of binary liquid alloys and activity coefficients of its constituent atoms are in agreement with the experiment. The study of concentration-concentration fluctuations at long wave length limit ($S_{CC}(0)$) and chemical short range order parameter (α_1) reveals that MgZn liquid binary alloy is a complex forming alloy and it is more ordered towards Zn-rich end than Mg-rich end. The surface tension of Zn is lowered with the addition of Mg. Mg atoms are more active at the surface than that in the bulk throughout the whole concentration range where as it is up to 40% of concentration of Zn in the case of Zn atoms. Mg atoms segregate to the surface in MgZn liquid binary alloy but the degree of segregation is low.

Keywords : Activity coefficients, concentration-concentration fluctuations, chemical short range order, surface tension, surface segregation, regression analysis, castibility, stoichiometric composition.

Introduction

The understanding of energetics in liquid binary alloys exhibiting anomalous behaviour requires much attention, although much work has been done for simple liquid alloys. The ternary systems are of great interest due to its industrial importance and for this, knowledge of its thermodynamic properties is useful. The analysis must begin with binary systems since thermodynamics of ternary systems rely on their binary systems. It is fairly known that the stability of liquid alloys is dependent on the interactions among the component atoms of the alloys^{1,2}. Theoreticians³⁻⁷ have shown considerable interest in explaining concentration dependent properties of liquid binary alloys due to their mechanical and technological importance⁸. The search for light weight solutions in the automotive industry has created a renewed interest in liquid alloys⁹.

Some Mg alloys are particularly interesting due to their glass forming activity and enable the optimization of steps necessary for light alloys production and design¹⁰. Because of its chemical, mechanical, physical and tribological properties, zinc is commonly utilized in engineering and scientific applications. In local foundries of China, zinc is used as bearing and bushing materials¹¹. Zinc is present in many commercial Mg alloys. Due to excellent castibility and high mechanical proper-

ties of zinc, its alloys are used as coating to enhance the corrosion resistance of cold rolled sheet steel¹². The phase diagram of liquid MgZn binary alloy is complicated^{13,14}. There exists a number of incongruently melting complexes Mg₂Zn₁₁, Mg₂Zn₃, MgZn and high temperature phase Mg₅₁Zn₂₃ (previously known as Mg₇Zn₃) along with a congruently melting phase MgZn₂. The free energy of mixing (ΔG_M) of liquid MgZn alloys is asymmetric about its equiatomic composition due to strong interactions between unlike atoms¹⁵⁻¹⁹ since the size effect (Ω_{Mg}/Ω_{Zn} , Ω is the atomic volume at specified temperature) of 1.557 and electronegativity difference ($EN = 1 - \exp(-0.25 d^2)$, d is the difference in electro negativity of the component atoms) of 0.0392 are small to account for anomalous behaviour. In such systems, it is assumed that some of the constituent atoms are randomly distributed while others coalesce into small groups bound by a sort of covalent bonding. Concentration fluctuations at long wavelength limit ($S_{CC}(0)$) and chemical short range order parameter (α_1)^{2,3,20,21} are powerful microscopic functions to understand the complex formation and phase segregation phenomena in liquid alloys. Hence, it is a better way²² to use $S_{CC}(0)$ for evaluating the extent of association in the liquid compared to direct analysis of thermodynamic data and to analyse the factors responsible for the formation of metallic glasses.

The surface tension of liquid binary alloys intervenes in nucleation from the vapour phase, in wetting, coating, casting^{23,24}, in mass transfer processes such as distillation, extraction or absorption, environmental engineering and biotechnology²⁵. It also explains intermolecular forces. The surface segregation is predicted in many liquid binary alloys²⁶ and is important in metallurgical operations in the study of catalytic activity²⁷⁻²⁹.

Margules equations³⁰⁻³³ are traditionally used to express excess thermodynamic properties of binary and multicomponent systems. The first order interaction parameters using Maclaurin infinite series considered by several workers³⁴⁻³⁹ are used here to express properties of liquid binary alloys.

Theoretical :

Thermodynamic properties :

Based on integral function of the binary system, the Maclaurin infinite series as $x_1 \rightarrow 1.0$ and $x_2 \rightarrow 1.0$ (x_1 and x_2 are the concentrations of first and second components of the binary system) may be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^{xs} = & (\Delta G^{xs})_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} + \left(\frac{\delta \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} \\ & X_2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2^2} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} X_2^2 \\ & + \frac{1}{3!} \left(\frac{\delta^3 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2^3} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} X_2^3 + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^{xs} = & (\Delta G^{xs})_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} + \left(\frac{\delta \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} \\ & X_1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1^2} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} X_1^2 \\ & + \frac{1}{3!} \left(\frac{\delta^3 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1^3} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} X_1^3 + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

imposing the boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^{xs} & \rightarrow 0 & \text{as } X_1 & \rightarrow 1.0 \\ \Delta G^{xs} & \rightarrow 0 & \text{as } X_2 & \rightarrow 1.0 \end{aligned}$$

Eqs. (1) and (2) reduce to

$$\sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{r!} \left(\frac{\delta^r \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2^r} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} = 0 \quad (3)$$

and

$$\sum_{r=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{r!} \left(\frac{\delta^r \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1^r} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Using eqs. (3) and (4), eqs. (1) and (2) are, respectively, modified as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^{xs} = & X_1 X_2 \left[\left(\frac{\delta \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} + X_2 \right. \\ & \left. \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2^2} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} \right\} + X_2^2 \right. \\ & \left. \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2^2} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{1}{3!} \left(\frac{\delta^3 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_2^3} \right)_{x_1 \rightarrow 1.0} + \dots \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^{xs} = & X_1 X_2 \left[\left(\frac{\delta \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} + X_1 \right. \\ & \left. \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1^2} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} \right\} + X_1^2 \right. \\ & \left. \left\{ \left(\frac{\delta \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\delta^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1^2} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{1}{3!} \left(\frac{\delta^3 \Delta G^{xs}}{\delta X_1^3} \right)_{x_2 \rightarrow 1.0} + \dots \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Equations

$$RT \ln r_1 = \Delta G^{xs} + (1-X_1) \frac{d\Delta G^{xs}}{dX_1} \quad (7a)$$

$$RT \ln r_2 = \Delta G^{xs} + (1-X_2) \frac{d\Delta G^{xs}}{dX_2} \quad (7b)$$

are used in converting the above derivatives for the binary systems. Eqs. (7) yield the relations.

$$\ln r_1^0(2) = \left(\frac{d\Delta G^{xs}}{dX_1} \right)_{X_2 \rightarrow 1.0} \frac{1}{RT} \text{ as } X_2 \rightarrow 1.0$$

$$\ln r_2^0(1) = \left(\frac{d\Delta G^{xs}}{dX_2} \right)_{X_1 \rightarrow 1.0} \frac{1}{RT} \text{ as } X_1 \rightarrow 1.0$$

Differentiating eq. (7a) with respect to X_1 and imposing condition $X_2 \rightarrow 1.0$ and eq. (7b) with respect to X_2 and imposing condition $X_1 \rightarrow 1.0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d \ln r_1}{dX_1} \right)_{X_2 \rightarrow 1.0} &= \left(\frac{d^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{dX_1^2} \right)_{X_2 \rightarrow 1.0} \frac{1}{RT} \\ &= \epsilon_1^1(2) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d \ln r_2}{dX_2} \right)_{X_1 \rightarrow 1.0} &= \left(\frac{d^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{dX_2^2} \right)_{X_1 \rightarrow 1.0} \frac{1}{RT} \\ &= \epsilon_2^2(1) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The process of differentiation may be repeated several times to obtain the relationship between higher order derivatives and interaction parameters and as such ΔG^{xs} of the binary system may be expressed as the summation of eqs. (5) and (6).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta G^{xs}}{RT} &= X_1 X_2 \left[\ln r_2^0(1) + X_2 \left\{ \ln r_2^0 + \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_2^2(1) \right\} + X_2^2 \dots \right] + X_1 X_2 \\ &\left[\ln r_1^0(2) + X_1 \left\{ \ln r_1^0(2) + \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_1^1(2) \right\} \right] \\ &+ X_1^2 \dots \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= X_1 X_2 \left[\ln r_2^0(1) + \ln r_2^0(2) + X_2 \left\{ \ln r_2^0(1) + \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_2^2(1) \right\} + X_1 \left\{ \ln r_1^0(2) + \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_1^1(2) \right\} + X_2^2 \dots + X_1^2 \dots \right] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Higher order terms in eq. (10) is unavoidable and the above equation is adjusted by the method involving repeated differentiation as described below by retaining the above functional form. Let eq. (10) be redesignated as

$$\frac{\Delta G^{xs}}{RT} = X_1 X_2 [a_1 + a_2 X_2 + X_1 X_2 (a_3 + a_4 X_2)] \quad (11)$$

By repeated differentiation of eq. (11), separately, with respect to X_2 with restriction $X_1 \rightarrow 1.0$ and X_1 with $X_2 \rightarrow 1.0$, we have

$$\left(\frac{d\Delta G^{xs}}{dX_2} \right)_{X_1 \rightarrow 1.0} \frac{1}{RT} = \ln r_2^0(1) = a_1$$

$$\left(\frac{d^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{dX_2^2} \right)_{X_1 \rightarrow 1.0} \frac{1}{RT} = \epsilon_2^2(1)$$

$$= -2(a_1 - a_2 - a_3)$$

$$\left(\frac{d\Delta G^{xs}}{dX_1} \right)_{X_2 \rightarrow 1.0} \frac{1}{RT}$$

$$= \ln r_2^0(2) = a_1 + a_2$$

$$\left(\frac{d^2 \Delta G^{xs}}{dX_1^2} \right)_{X_2 \rightarrow 1.0} \frac{1}{RT}$$

$$= \epsilon_2^2(2) = -2(a_1 + 2a_2 - a_3 - a_4)$$

Solution of the above equations yield

$$a_1 = \ln r_2^0(1)$$

$$a_2 = \ln r_1^0(2) - \ln r_2^0(1)$$

$$a_3 = \frac{1}{2} \epsilon_2^2(1) - \ln r_1^0(2) + 2 \ln r_2^0(1)$$

$$a_4 = \frac{1}{2} [\epsilon_1^2(2) - \epsilon_2^2(1)] + 3 [\ln r_1^0(2) - \ln r_2^0(1)]$$

The activity coefficients may be obtained from eqs. (7) and (11) as

$$\ln r_1 = X_2^2 [a_1 - a_2(1 - 2X_2) + 2X_1X_2(a_3 + a_4X_2) - X_1^2(a_3 + 2a_4X_2)] \quad (12)$$

$$\ln r_2 = X_1^2 [a_1 + 2a_2X_2 + a_3X_2(2 - 3X_2) + a_4X_2^2(3 - 4X_2)] \quad (13)$$

Concentration-concentration fluctuations at long wavelength limit ($S_{CC}(0)$) and chemical short range order parameter (α_1) :

Concentration-concentration fluctuation at long wavelength limit ($S_{CC}(0)$) is widely used to understand the stability of the binary mixture and may be obtained theoretically as

$$S_{CC}(0) = RT \left(\frac{\partial^2 \Delta GM}{\partial X_1^2} \right)_{T,P,N} \quad (14)$$

where,

$\Delta GM = X_1 \ln X_1 + X_2 \ln X_2 + \Delta G^{xs}$
on differentiation and using eq. (11), one gets

$$S_{CC}(0) = \left[\frac{1}{X_1X_2} - 2(a_1 + 2a_2 - a_3 - a_4) + 6X_1(a_2 - 2a_3 - 3a_4) + 4X_1^2 \{3a_3 + a_4(9 - 5X_1)\}^{-1} \right] \quad (15)$$

The Warren-Cowley^{40,41} short range order parameter (α_1) is computed to quantify the degree of order. α_1 can be determined experimentally from number correlation function ($S_{NN}(q)$) and number concentration correlation function ($S_{NC}(q)$). However, the determination of these two parameters is difficult for all types of binary alloys^{42,43} But α_1 may be obtained theoretically^{20,21} as

$$a_1 = \frac{(S - 1)}{(S(Z - 1) + 1)} \quad (16)$$

$$S = \frac{S_{CC}(0)}{S_{CC}(0)_{id}} \quad (17)$$

Z is the co-ordination number which is taken as 12 for our purpose and $S_{CC}(0)_{id} = X_1X_2$.

Surface tension :

The surface tension of complex forming liquid alloys is given by^{19,20,44}

$$\sigma = \sigma_1 + \left(\frac{RT}{A} \right) \left[\ln \left(\frac{X_1^s}{X_1} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{r_1^s}{r_1} \right) \right] \quad (18a)$$

$$= \sigma_2 + \left(\frac{RT}{A} \right) \left[\ln \left(\frac{X_2^s}{X_2} \right) + \ln \left(\frac{r_2^s}{r_2} \right) \right] \quad (18b)$$

where σ_1 and σ_2 are the surface tension of pure components of the binary liquid alloys and A is the mean atomic surface area. X_i^s and r_i^s ($i = 1, 2$) refer, respectively, to the concentrations and activity coefficients of the i -th component at the surface. r_i^s is related to r_i ^{20,24} as

$$\ln r_i^s = p (\ln r_i \text{ containing } X_i^s \text{ in place of } X_i) + q \ln r_i \quad (19)$$

Results and discussion

The constants of eq. (11) are determined by the regressional analysis of the integral excess free energy of mixing of liquid MgZn alloy⁴⁵. The assessed values of the first order interaction parameters from the present function along with the selected values of Hultgren *et al.*⁴⁵ are tabulated in Table 1. Table 1 shows that the evaluated values of free energy of mixing $\left(\frac{\Delta G^{xs}}{RT} \right)$ are

Table 1. Evaluated and experimental excess free energy of mixing $\left(\frac{\Delta G^{xs}}{RT} \right)$ of MgZn liquid binary alloy at 923 K

Regressional values $a_1 = -2.141104$, $a_2 = 0.250264$,
 $a_3 = 2.8157$, $a_4 = -3.7267$

$\left(\frac{\Delta G^{xs}}{RT} \right)$	X_2	Present	Expt. ⁴⁵
	0.1	-0.1701	-0.1751
	0.2	-0.2934	-0.2975
	0.3	-0.3926	-0.3905
	0.4	-0.4651	-0.4615
	0.5	-0.5050	-0.5070
	0.6	-0.5071	-0.5165
	0.7	-0.4679	-0.4772
	0.8	-0.3784	-0.3788
	0.9	-0.2279	-0.2173
$\ln \gamma_{Zn}$		-2.141104	-2.465104
$\ln \gamma_{Mg}$		-2.391368	-2.733368
$\epsilon_1^1(2)$		3.461264	
$\epsilon_2^2(1)$		9.413080	

in close agreement with the experimental values. The computed values of $\ln r$ [$r = r_1/r_2$; r_1, r_2 are calculated, respectively, via eqs. (12) and (13)] for liquid MgZn binary alloy versus concentration X_2 are given in Table 2 together with the experimental values⁴⁵ and other theoretical values²⁰ obtained using grand partition function in the frame work of quasi lattice theory. The present values are in agreement with the experimental values and are better than the previous values²⁰.

X_2	Present	Previous theoretical value ²⁰	Expt. ⁴⁵
0.1	1.433	1.611	1.317
0.2	1.052	1.252	1.122
0.3	0.818	0.860	0.867
0.4	0.595	0.444	0.566
0.5	0.295	0.154	0.236
0.6	-0.128	-0.417	-0.172
0.7	-0.674	-0.843	-0.629
0.8	-1.301	-1.254	-1.285
0.9	-1.917	-1.640	-1.855

The theoretical values of $S_{CC}(0)$ are computed through eq. (15). Values of $S_{CC}(0)$ obtained directly from observed activity data following the equalities

$$S_{CC}(0) = (1 - X_1)a_1 \left(\frac{\partial a_1}{\partial X_1} \right)_{T,P,N}^{-1} = (1 - X_2)a_2 \left(\frac{\partial a_2}{\partial X_2} \right)_{T,P,N}^{-1}$$

(a_1, a_2 are the activities of first and second components of the liquid binary alloys) are usually termed as experimental values of $S_{CC}(0)$. The computed and experimental values⁴⁵ of $S_{CC}(0)$ are shown in the upper part of Fig. 1 along with other theoretical values²² and $S_{CC}(0)_{id}$. From $S_{CC}(0) < S_{CC}(0)_{id}$, the existence of chemical ordering leading to complex formation is expected. The minimum in $S_{CC}(0)$ occurs around stoichiometric composition MgZn₂.

α_1 is evaluated through eq. (16) and is presented in the lower part of Fig. 1. α_1 provides immediate insight into the local arrangement of atoms in the liquid alloys. $\alpha_1 = 0$ indicates a random distribution of atoms where as $\alpha_1 > 0$ refers to like atoms pairing and $\alpha_1 < 0$ corres-

Fig. 1. Variation of concentration-concentration fluctuations along wavelength limit (upper part) and chemical short range order (lower part) for MgZn liquid binary alloy at 923 K. (—) present, (xxx) Expt.⁴⁵, ($\Delta\Delta\Delta$) other theoretical value²⁰, ($\bullet\bullet\bullet$) ideal value; (---) present.

ponds to unlike atoms pairing as nearest neighbours. The values of α_1 remain negative throughout the whole composition range. The minimum value of α_1 around $X_2 = 0.7$ infers that Zn-rich end is more ordered than Mg-rich end.

Eqs. (18) have been solved numerically to compute surface tension (σ) and surface concentration (X_1^s) of liquid MgZn binary alloy. p and q are surface coordination fractions which are fractions of total number of nearest neighbours by an atom within the layer in which it lies and that in the adjoining layer, so that $p + 2q = 1$. p and q are treated as parameters and are taken as 0.5 and 0.25, respectively. The mean atomic surface area, A , is calculated through the relation⁴⁶,

$$A = 1.2 (V_M)^{2/3}$$

where V_M is the volume of the alloy. We have used here the linear volume of the alloy,

$$V_M = X_1 V_1 + X_2 V_2$$

Here, $V_1 = 2.67622 \times 10^{-23} \text{ cm}^3$ and $V_2 = 1.71914 \times$

10^{-23} cm^3 are the volumes of Mg and Zn, respectively, at 923 K based on the density data of Brandes⁴⁷. The surface tension of the component elements of the liquid alloy at the specified temperature are also taken from the same data⁴⁷.

The computed values of surface tension (σ) versus concentration for liquid MgZn alloy at 923 K are depicted in Fig. 2. Because of lack of experimental data we are not able to compare our theoretical values with experimental values. A comparative study reveals that Mg atoms lower the surface tension of Zn. The surface tension of MgZn liquid alloy is lower than its ideal value

$$\sum X_i \sigma_i \text{ up to } X_2 = 0.5 \text{ and higher after } X_2 > 0.5.$$

The activity coefficients of Mg and Zn at the surface and in the bulk and surface concentration of Mg in liquid MgZn binary alloy at $T = 923 \text{ K}$ are given in Table 3. Table 3 shows that the activity coefficients of Mg at the surface are more than that of in the bulk throughout the

Fig. 2. Surface tension MgZn liquid alloys at 923 K. (—) present value.

whole concentration range. Mg atoms are more active at the surface than those in the bulk in MgZn liquid alloy at all compositions. But it is not same for Zn atoms. The activity coefficients of Zn are less at the surface than that of in the bulk up to $X_1 = 0.5$ and reverse is the case after this concentration. It is also revealed from Table 3 that Mg atoms segregate to the surface at all bulk concentration of Mg. However, degree of segregation is low.

Table 3. Activity coefficients of Mg and Zn in the bulk (r) and at the surface (r^S) and surface concentration of Mg in MgZn liquid binary alloy at 923 K

X_1	Mg		Zn		X_1^S
	$r (=r_1)$	$R^S (=r_1^S)$	$r (=r_2)$	$R^S (=r_2^S)$	
0.1	0.1432	0.2669	0.9747	0.9617	0.152
0.2	0.2417	0.4334	0.8881	0.8483	0.297
0.3	0.3868	0.6247	0.7596	0.7059	0.448
0.4	0.5525	0.7428	0.6279	0.5889	0.604
0.5	0.6981	0.8600	0.5195	0.5091	0.738
0.6	0.7999	0.9130	0.4408	0.4441	0.829
0.7	0.8649	0.9470	0.3816	0.3850	0.891
0.8	0.9166	0.9716	0.3199	0.3263	0.938
0.9	0.9687	0.9908	0.2309	0.2634	0.976

Same interaction parameters have been considered for the calculation of bulk properties like excess free energy of mixing and activity coefficients, microscopic properties like concentration-concentration fluctuations at long wave length limit and chemical short range order parameters and surface properties like surface tension and surface segregation.

Thus the first order interaction parameters using Maclaurin infinite series may successfully be used to study the concentration dependent thermodynamic properties as well as surface properties of liquid alloys.

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